

Strategies for Minimizing The Impact Of Corporate Conspiracy On Employees` Productivity In Public Tertiary Institutions In Rivers State

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Abstract: This study examined strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on employees` productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. From a population of 123 lecturers, a census survey sampling was engaged. A four-point response options questionnaire was used for data collection, and it was validated by three experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach’s alpha which yielded coefficients of 0.73 and 0.75. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions and measure the spread in respondents` opinions, while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that corporate conspiracy very highly, impacts negatively with very highly strategies available for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers` productivity. Consequently, it was concluded that if tertiary institutions managements are not careful of corporate conspiracy and device a better way of handling it, the productivity of lecturers will continue to lower with serious negative effect on the students` performance and overall objectives of the tertiary institutions. Based on the findings, it was recommended that public tertiary institutions managements should among others adopt two-way communication to facilitate understanding, good quality employee organizational relationship to bring transparency and commitment, Goal-Setting Theory to examine the extent to which goal setting and feedback drive employees (lecturers) productivity in the tertiary institutions.

Keywords: *Strategies For Minimizing Corporate Conspiracy, Impact Of Corporate Conspiracy, Lecturers, Employees` Productivity.*

Introduction

Although there appear to be strategies for minimizing corporate conspiracy in organizations, financial instability and the needless pursuit of political and economic power within organizations (tertiary institutions) have made room for employers and employees to engage in corporate conspiracy and conspiracy theory in order to primarily satisfy their interests (Mekuri-Ndimele, 2025).

Corporate Conspiracy (CC)

A corporate conspiracy is when two or more people in a corporation (a tertiary institution) band together to commit crimes or deceive others; this can include gossip, defamation, or defrauding the government, regulatory bodies, investors, or the public. The goal is usually to make money, gain promotion, and gain popularity through deceit or misrepresentation (Faster Capital, 2024). Corporate conspiracy also refers to the covert and occasionally unlawful actions of people, companies, and their executives in order to accomplish a shared objective. This can also involve witch-hunting, defamation, and maligning, which can cause employees to feel more anxious about their jobs, and can negatively affect their productivity (Mekuri-Ndimele, 2025). The intricacy of these acts has hurt the worker, public and smaller businesses, making it difficult for law enforcement and regulators to find and bring charges against them. According to van Prooijen

and de Vries (2016), corporate conspiracy is defined as the interpretive beliefs of employees (lecturers at tertiary institutions) who secretly meet to achieve goals that are typically seen as evil and vicious and who complain about their bosses, subordinates, or co-workers. This can potentially result in employee withdrawal in the place of work.

Employees (Lecturers) Withdrawal (ELW)

Withdrawal behaviours (interest) are the reactions of an employee who is unhappy with their working conditions; a variety of volunteer activities outside of the extra jobs are seen as essential to organisational effectiveness; and it is clear that these reactions negatively impact the success of employment activities. Employee disengagement is considered one of the detrimental attitudes (negative impact) connected to human resource management as a result of corporate collusion. These withdrawals reflect a portion of the personnel that avoids overwhelming the work environment and occasionally putting in their best effort (Carpenter & Berry, 2017). There may be times when an employee starts to leave both his job and his association with the company as a result of conspiracy. Employee volunteer delays, absenteeism, negligence, and plans to quit the organisation because of corporate and conspiratorial beliefs, which are some examples of these behaviours, according to Rurkkhum (2018).

Conspiracy theories suggest that organisations act in secretive, malicious ways to achieve their own self-interested goals. Recent

research suggests that corporate conspiracies may actually lower employee productivity (Van Prooijen & Jostmann, 2013). According to a popular conspiracy theory, people are being misinformed about the reality of climate change, and the 9/11 attacks were "inside job" (Douglas, Ana, & Leite, 2017). According to conspiracy theories, events were covered up by a strong and evil cabal. Accordingly, the secret operations of malicious groups that hide information to achieve their own goals are the primary causes of significant occurrences (Jolly, Meleady & Douglas, 2019; Douglas & Sutton, 2018). Some employees of higher institutions have lied to management about their colleagues in order to gain favour. They have done things like falsifying of results, collect bribes, submit petitions, engage in sexual harassment, and skip classes. Numerous corporate or organisational conspiracy theories have emerged at postsecondary institutions as a result of the competition for political and economic dominance and the need for instant pleasure.

Corporate or Organizational Conspiracy Theories and Their Impact (COCTTI)

According to Mekuri-Ndimele (2025), conspiracy theories about companies or organisations are the idea that powerful people or groups like managers in higher education institutions are secretly pursuing a malevolent objective. For example, managers may intentionally choose to fire a worker or select a preferred candidate for a job (appointment) who may not be qualified. In particular, rumours and gossip tend to implicate individuals more often than groups, and they lower motivation, attendance rates at meetings and classes, and publications. Conspiracy theories among individuals within organisations can also have a negative effect on the productivity of lecturers (employees) (Douglas, Ana & Leite, 2017). Conspiracy theories about corporations are significant because they actually affect people's safety, relationships, and health. They evoke negative feelings rather than logical arguments, which leads to conspiracy theories. Employee productivity is negatively impacted by corporate conspiracy theories, which are intimately linked to psychological motivations (Grzesiak-Feldman, 2013). Corporate conspiracies can have disastrous, far-reaching effects. Lower interest, emotional distress, increased costs, less competition, and less innovation in the market, which are all possible outcomes. Additionally, it can erode public confidence in the business community (universities) and foster feelings of unfairness and injustice (Benedict, 2021). In particular, instructors may be more inclined to think about quitting their company if they have a poor opinion of it.

Employees (Lecturers) (EL)

In this study, lecturers and employees are synonymous. Workers are crucial elements in the fields of labour economics, human resource management, and employment law. According to Olumba et al. (2023), workers are those who have a contract with their employer that grants the employer the authority to oversee and manage their labour. Lecturers are post-secondary teachers employed by the organisation to instruct in a college or university. They are employed by the tertiary institutions. In the context of tertiary institutions, conspiracy may result in ineffective and inefficient performance by lecturers, who are hired to teach students through lectures, seminars, tutorials, fieldwork, and online learning; prepare course materials, including presentations and assignments; conduct research in their area of expertise; publish scholarly journal articles or books; sit on academic committees; mentor, manage, and supervise other staff; develop curricula; and

meaningfully engage students and the public (Zippia Team, 2025). The lecturers' job descriptions include performance requirements such as developing platform-neutral course materials and curricula, working with other academics and lecturers to improve teaching strategies and broaden knowledge, completing and grading homework, administering examinations and assessments, conducting research and producing papers, proposals, journal articles, and books, and taking part in internal and external meetings, conferences, and publications. A university lecturer's job description includes assisting students and colleagues, reading widely and producing published work in the field to keep current, and taking part in institutional training opportunities and initiatives (Mekuri-Ndimele & Ukata, 2024). Because lecturers have extremely demanding professions, corporate conspiracies have a tendency to have a negative effect on their performance.

Productivity (Performance) (PP)

Performance and productivity are used interchangeably in this study. The effective and economical utilisation of all resources is a necessary component of productivity. Time, people, expertise, data, money, equipment, physical space, energy, and materials are some examples of resources. According to Olumba et al. (2023), productivity is a quantitative indicator of the amount of output produced relative to the amount of input used. The efficacy and efficiency of a business (tertiary institutions) using labour and capital to produce goods and services is measured by productivity. The quantity and quality of output generated with the resources used is what Calabrese (2012) defines as productivity. Mustapha and Omorede (2017) claimed that the economist's perspective on productivity faces significant obstacles in the global public sector due to the unique characteristics of public service. Therefore, the degree to which lecturers fulfil their duties in terms of teaching, research, development, and community service tasks, duties, and activities meant to advance students' learning and help them meet their learning objectives is referred to as job performance. The degree to which academic staff members at postsecondary institutions accomplish a range of duties (such as teaching, research, and community service) has been characterised by scholars as the job performance of lecturers (Owan et al., 2020).

Employees Productivity (Lecturers Jobs Performance) (EPLJP)

In this study, productivity and job performance are used interchangeably. Thus, job performance is the extent to which lecturers carry out their responsibilities in terms of teaching, research, development, and community service tasks, as well as other responsibilities and activities designed to enhance students' learning and assist them in achieving their learning goals. Scholars have defined lecturers' job performance as the extent to which academic staff members at postsecondary institutions carry out a variety of tasks (including teaching, research, and community service) (Owan et al., 2020). A positive and supportive work environment, training and development, time and workload management, employee engagement, motivation and job satisfaction, rewards and recognition, and more all have an impact on employee productivity (Olumba et al, 2023; Davis & Taylor, 2020). Job performance is the extent to which lecturers fulfil their responsibilities, tasks, and activities pertaining to teaching, research, development, and community service in order to promote students' learning and the achievement of the desired educational goals. The degree to which academic staff members at postsecondary institutions fulfil a range of duties, such as teaching,

research, and community involvement, has been characterised by scholars as the job performance of lecturers (Owan et al., 2020).

According to Ukata and Agburuga (2024), academic staff job success is determined by the relationship between teaching attributes and academic accomplishment both within and outside of the classroom. Thus, corporate conspiracy may negatively affect academic staff members' job performance in a number of ways, including instructional efficacy, job dedication, job satisfaction, and incentive to perform. The potential long-term and substantial impact on students' and the nation's educational attainment makes lecturers' work performance essential and impossible to overestimate (Akah et al., 2022).

Theoretical Framework (TF)

The theory used in this study is the Goal-Setting Theory, which was created by Edwin Locke and Gary Latham in the 1960s and 1970s (Olumba et al., 2023). The goal-setting theory's central tenet is that performance and motivation are enhanced by the establishment of specific, difficult goals. The theory states that in order to effectively drive performance, objectives should adhere to the SMART framework, which stands for specified, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound. Furthermore, the idea contends that achieving goals requires accountability and feedback rather than corporate conspiracies and conspiracy theories. Ultimately, the goal-setting theory may be able to shed light on how lecturers who are actually employees performed in their emotional assignments. The study focusses on how to minimise the impact of corporate conspiracies on workers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state. The hypothesis could be applied, for example, to investigate how much goal-setting and feedback are used to improve university lecturers' job performance; it could also be applied to examine whether the objectives set for lecturers are clear, difficult, and attainable; and whether they receive feedback on how they are doing in relation to these objectives rather than conspire against the employee.

Strategies For Minimizing The Impact Of Corporate Conspiracy On Employees Productivity (SMICCEP)

Despite the challenges caused by corporate conspiracy, the following are some of the strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on employees' productivity (Tam, Lee & Kim, 2024):

➤ **Two-way Communication (TC)**

The conditions that lead to an unfavourable organisational climate where conspiratorial thinking thrives can be reduced because organisational climate contributes to organisational suspicion. Tam and Kim (2023) called for more research that uses the public relations lens to identify the antecedent variables of conspiratorial thinking, and they also identified organization-public relationship (OPR) quality as an antecedent variable of conspiratorial thinking. Current research has found the importance of two-way communication in fostering employee-organization relationships (EORs). Understanding, cooperation, and responsiveness are all facilitated by two-way communication (Grunig and Kim, 2021). Because workers are given the opportunity to influence organisational decision-making, it is a more moral method of relationship management in businesses and create room for fair hearing. The lack of two-way communication, on the other hand, represents an authoritarian workplace culture in which staff members do not feel encouraged to contribute to organisational decision-making.

➤ **Employee–Organization Relationship Quality (EORQ)**

Relational commitment (i.e., the degree to which one wishes to keep the relationship going), control mutuality (i.e., the degree to which one agrees who can decide on relational goals and routines), trust (i.e., confidence in the other party and willingness to open oneself), and relationship satisfaction (i.e., the degree to which one perceives that the benefits of staying in the relationship outweigh the costs) are some of the quality indicators that explain EORQ in employee communication. EORQ is enhanced when organisations adopt genuine practices, such as establishing openness and consistency through two-way communication (Lee & Kim, 2017).

➤ **Perceived Ethical Orientation (PEO)**

Perceived ethical orientation gauges an organization's propensity to place a higher priority on ethics in its procedures or results, whereas two-way communication assesses organisational behaviours that demonstrate attempts to listen to and interact with the public, including workers. The public's assessment of the moral standards that an organisation employs to direct and defend its choices and activities is reflected in its perceived ethical orientation. Furthermore, since moral theory explains that an act or deed is assessed as ethical based on its "process" rather than its "outcomes," an organization's actions will become intrinsically moral if there is a due process established to interact with workers at all times. According to Grunig and Kim (2021), the public's opinions or assessments of an organization's moral conduct may be significantly influenced by the inclusion of interests (i.e., two-way communication). Trust and loyalty are greatly increased by an organization's ethical behaviour. One of the negative outcomes of a lack of ethical orientation could be dishonesty in the workplace.

➤ **Whistleblowing Potential (WP)**

Whistleblowing is defined as "the disclosure by organisation members (former or current) to persons or organisations that may be able to effect action of illegal, immoral, or illegitimate practices under the control of their employers." While employees are not required to report organisational misconduct, their disclosure of the misconduct to an outside party demonstrated a desire to address the misconduct. When there is a high frequency of observed unethical behaviours, employees are more likely to want to engage in external whistleblowing for safety, even though it is best for employees to do so within their organisations so that management can handle the reports of observed unethical behaviours internally (Kaptein, 2022). According to Teamflect (2025), if you are following current trends in Human Resources Management, you will understand why putting employee communication initiatives into practice is so popular. Everything from performance and productivity to overall employee engagement and retention rates is impacted by internal communication. Therefore, the following tactics are employed to lessen the effects of corporate conspiracies in tertiary institutions.

➤ **Enhances Crisis Management (ECM)**

Businesses that have efficient internal communications teams and clear internal communication procedures are better equipped to handle change and emergencies.

➤ **Builds Trust (BT)**

Building trust between employees and employers can be achieved most effectively by communicating important facts and future plans to your staff.

➤ **Crisis Communication (CC)**

The workplace is a volatile environment, internal communications will not always be conducted for constructive purposes. Any internal communication that results from a crisis or urgent situation is referred to as crisis communication. An effective crisis communication plan guarantees that companies can promptly handle issues and educate staff members on what to do.

➤ **Subjects and Moderating Variables of the Study (SMVS)**

The study's subjects are male and female lecturers (workers) with varying degrees of years of teaching experience and educational attainment who are aware of ways to reduce the negative effects of corporate conspiracy on their productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers State. According to Ezenwafor and Ukata (2022a), a lecturer's ability to exhibit understanding of corporate conspiracy is influenced by their age, years of teaching experience, educational background, and training and retraining. Because lecturers with more than 10 years of experience teaching in tertiary institutions are expected to have a greater understanding of the strategies for minimising the impact of corporate conspiracy on employees' productivity than those with 6 to 10 and 1 to 5 years of experience, Ukata and Okeke (2023) and Ukata and Nmihelle (2022) asserted that age and teaching experience are two factors that influence lecturers' knowledge of these strategies. Furthermore, due to their expertise, lecturers with advanced degrees such as PhDs and M.Sc./M.Ed. are expected to know more

about how to reduce the negative effects of corporate conspiracies on workers' productivity than those with HNDs, B.Sc., or B.Ed. (Ukata & Udeh, 2022; Ezenwafor & Ukata, 2022b). In order to determine how to reduce the impact of corporate conspiracy on employees' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state, the study examined the respondents' years of teaching experience and educational attainment (three levels of moderating variables).

➤ **Statement of the Problem (SP)**

In order to largely meet their interests, employers and employees appear to have made place for corporate conspiracies and conspiracy theories as a result of the economic unrest and the needless pursuit of political and economic power within the organisations (tertiary institutions). Instead of employing more effective methods, such Goal-Setting Theory, to assign tasks, collect data, and assess lecturers' performance, managers in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state seem to rely more on corporate conspiracies and conspiracy theory. The purpose of this study is to determine "strategies for minimising the impact of corporate conspiracy on employees' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state," as it is possible that they are unaware of the issues related to corporate conspiracy, how it affects lecturers' productivity, and how to minimise it. Since no other study has a specific goal like this, the results of this one will fill the knowledge gap and provide decision makers with empirical facts in addressing related problems of this study.

Methodology

The research design used in the study was a descriptive survey. Since it aimed to gather the opinions of male and female lecturers on how to reduce the effect of corporate conspiracy on employees' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state, a descriptive survey research methodology was judged appropriate. Twelve lecturers from the Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku (57), Rivers State University (21) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (12), Captain Elechi Amadi (14) and Ken Sarowiwa Polytechnic (10), made up the study's population. Due to its reasonable size, the census survey technique was used to sample all 123 lecturers. A self-created four-point response questionnaire called "Strategies for Minimizing the Impact of Corporate Conspiracy on Employees' Productivity (SMICCEP)" was used to collect the data. Sections one and two had 10 and 8 items, respectively, and were scored as medium (2.50 - 3.49), lowly (1.50 - 2.49), highly (3.50 - 4.49), and very highly (4.50 - 5.00). Ten University of Uyo lecturers who were not included in the study population were given the instrument. The dependability coefficient was calculated using Cronbach's alpha, which produced alpha values of 0.73 and 0.75. The instruments' strong reliability coefficients show their dependability. With the help of three research assistants who had received adequate training on the procedures to be followed, the researchers individually delivered copies of the questionnaire to the respondents at their schools. Three specialists from Nnamdi Azikiwe University's Faculty of Education in Awka validated the questionnaire's face and substance. The reliability of the instrument was established using the measure of internal consistency approach. Prior to beginning the study, the researchers went to each postsecondary school and obtained permission from the appropriate department heads. The researchers and assistants then went to each school and gave the department heads the necessary number of copies of the instrument to provide to the lecturers for completion. They then returned five working days later to collect the finished copies. The instrument was correctly filled out, retrieved, and utilised for the data analysis in 110 duplicates. To answer the two study questions and determine how homogeneous or diverse the respondents' opinions were in relation to the questionnaire items and the aggregated mean, the arithmetic mean and standard deviation were employed. The null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using the one-way analysis variance (ANOVA). Since the ANOVA measured a single categorical independent variable with three levels of moderating variables, it was utilised for the null hypotheses. When the computed significant (Sig.) value, or p-value, was more than or equal to (\geq) the alpha value of 0.05, a null hypothesis was accepted. If not, the null hypothesis was disproved.

Version 25 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse the data.

Result Presentation, Analysis and Discussion (RPAD)

➤ **Research Question 1**

How does corporate conspiracy impact on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state?

Table 1: Respondents' mean ratings on how corporate conspiracy impact on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state

SN	How corporate conspiracy impact on lecturers' productivity	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1	It wrongly implicates individuals and reduce motivation at work	4.53	.81	Very Highly
2	It reduces the rate of attending classes to teach students	4.51	.82	Very Highly
3	It reduces the rate of attending meetings to meaningfully contribute	4.54	.81	Very Highly
4	It lowers my interest in publications	4.52	.80	Very Highly
5	It impacts on my emotions being badly	4.53	.82	Very Highly
6	It brings ill-health, relationships and safety	4.54	.83	Very Highly
7	It kills good relationships in the workplace	4.51	.80	Very Highly
8	corporate conspiracy makes lecturers look unsafety	4.52	.82	Very Highly
9	It undermines lecturers' efforts in the workplace	4.54	.83	Very Highly
10	Corporate conspiracy increases innovation	4.51	.80	Very Highly
	Aggregated Mean	4.53		Very Highly

Table 1 shows that all the 10 have very highly negative impacts of corporate conspiracy with mean scores that ranged from 4.51- 4.54. In the same manner, the aggregated mean score of 4.53 also shows that corporate conspiracy very highly impacts negatively on lecturers' productivity. The standard deviations for the 10 listed items ranged within 0.80 to 0.83, which shows that respondents were homogeneous in their opinions that all the mentioned shows that corporate conspiracy very highly, impacts negatively on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state.

➤ **Research Question 2**

What are the strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state?

Table 1: Respondents' mean ratings on strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity

SN	Strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
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1	Two-way communication facilitates of understanding, collaboration, responsiveness in organization and reduce suspicion	4.52	.80	Very Highly
2	Good quality employee organizational relationship brings transparency and commitment	4.53	.81	Very Highly
3	Whistleblowing assist organization to correct unethical behaviour	4.54	.82	Very Highly
4	Perceived ethical orientation assist organization to prioritize ethics in organization	4.51	.81	Very Highly
5	Enhances crisis management helps organization navigate through crises period	4.54	.82	Very Highly
6	Building trust boost the confidence of employees and ensure they are aware of key information in organizations as such reduce anxiety	4.51	.84	Very Highly
7	Crisis communication ensure organizations quickly address conspiracy challenges	4.53	.83	Very Highly
	Aggregated Mean	4.52		Very Highly

Table 2 shows that all the 8 items are very highly strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy with mean scores that ranged from 4.51- 4.54. In the same manner, the aggregated mean score of 4.52 also shows very highly strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity. The standard deviations for the 8 listed items ranged within 0.80 to 0.84, which shows that respondents were homogeneous in their opinions that all the mentioned were very highly strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state.

Hypotheses Testing (HT)

➤ Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female lecturers on how corporate conspiracy impacts on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state based on their years of experience.

Table 3: ANOVA summary of male and female lecturers on how corporate conspiracy impact on lecturers' productivity based on their years of experience.

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal.	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	2.358	2	1.429	1.388	.293	Accept H ₀₁
Within Groups	53.357	113	.787			
Total	57.615	115				

Table 3 shows a calculated F-value of 1.38 with a significant (sig.) p-value of 0.29 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 ($0.29 > 0.05$) at degrees of freedom of 2 and 113. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female lecturers on how corporate conspiracy impacts on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers

state based on their years of experience.

Hypothesis 2

Male and female lecturers do not differ in their mean rating on the strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state.

Table 4: ANOVA summary of male and female lecturers on the strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity based educational attainment

Sources of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal.	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	2.458	2	1.529	1.398	.283	Accept H ₀₁
Within Groups	53.557	113	.887			
Total	57.715	115				

Table 4 shows a calculated F-value of 1.39 with a significant (sig.) p-value of 0.28 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 (0.28 > 0.05) at degrees of freedom of 2 and 113. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) was accepted. This means that male and female lecturers do not differ in their mean rating on the strategies for minimizing the impact of corporate conspiracy on lecturers' productivity in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state based on their educational attainment.

Discussion

The study's findings show that corporate collusion significantly reduces lecturers' productivity. The findings corroborate the claim made by Douglas, Ana, and Leite (2017) that rumours and gossip more often place the blame incorrectly on specific people and have a negative impact on publications, motivation, and attendance at meetings and lectures. Additionally, they discovered that conspiracy ideas among workers within businesses can negatively impact professors' output. The findings lend more credence to Grzesiak-Feldman's (2013) claimed that psychological incentives and decreased worker productivity are intimately related to corporate conspiracy ideas. Corporate plots can have catastrophic, long-lasting consequences. Possible implications include decreased interest, emotional suffering, more expenses, reduced competition, and less market innovation. Furthermore, it might increase sentiments of unfairness and injustice and weaken public trust in the business community (tertiary institutions) (Benedict, 2021). The study's conclusions also demonstrate some very effective methods for reducing the effect of corporate conspiracies on instructors' output. According to Tam, Lee, and Kim (2024), Grunig and Kim (2021), Lee and Kim (2017), Kaptein (2022), and Teamflect (2025), two-way communication promotes understanding, collaboration, and responsiveness within the organisation and reduces suspicion; positive employee-organization relationships bring transparency and dedication to duties; whistleblowing helps organisations correct unethical behaviour; perceived ethical orientation helps organisations prioritise ethics within the organisation; and improved crisis

management helps organisations navigate through times of crisis and succeed.

The results of the study also showed that lecturers in public tertiary institutions do not significantly differ in their mean assessments of the effects of corporate conspiracy and tactics for minimising it on their productivity based on their years of experience and educational level. Furthermore, the findings corroborate the assertions of Ezenwafor and Ukata (2022a) that lecturers' age, training and retraining, educational background, and years of teaching experience all affect how well they demonstrate an awareness of corporate conspiracy. Accordingly, Ukata and Okeke (2023) and Ukata and Nmiehelle (2022) claimed that lecturers' understanding of the effects of corporate conspiracies and methods for reducing them on worker productivity is influenced by two factors: age and prior teaching experience. This is due to the fact that instructors with over ten years of university teaching experience are anticipated to be more knowledgeable about the effects of corporate conspiracies on worker productivity and how to mitigate them than instructors with six to ten and one to five years of experience.

Given that the study shows that corporate conspiracy has a major detrimental effect on lecturers' productivity, management of tertiary institutions should be extremely cautious when it comes to corporate conspiracy theories and implement strategies like two-way communication, which promotes understanding, collaboration, and responsiveness in the workplace and reduces suspicion, whistleblowing, which helps organisations correct unethical behaviour, and good employee organisational relationships, which bring transparency and commitment to duties, among others, to minimise the impact of corporate conspiracy on employees' productivity.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study's discussions, it was determined that if managements of tertiary institutions do not take precautions to prevent conspiracy and devise better strategies, such

as two-way communication to promote understanding, collaboration, responsiveness in the organisation, and reduce suspicion, good employee organisational relationships to bring transparency and commitment to duties, whistleblowing to help organisations correct unethical behaviour, and the Goal-Setting Theory, which was developed by Edwin Locke and Gary Latham in the 1960s and 1970s, the productivity of lecturers will continue to decline, with a significant negative impact on student performance and the universities' overall goals.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Due to the detrimental effects of corporate conspiracy and conspiracy theories, managers of public tertiary institutions in Rivers State should exercise extreme caution. The goal-setting theory, which was developed by Edwin Locke and Gary Latham in the 1960s and 1970s, should be adopted by the management of tertiary institutions in order to investigate the degree to which goal-setting and feedback are utilised to motivate university professors. The idea should also be applied to examine if the objectives set for lecturers are clear, difficult, and attainable, as well as whether they receive feedback on how well they are doing in relation to these objectives. Finally, the Goal-Setting Theory contributes to the understanding of how lecturers (workers) carried out their assigned tasks with their feelings.

2. In order to reduce the impact of corporate conspiracy on the productivity of lecturers in public tertiary institutions in Rivers state, the management of these institutions should implement the following strategies: whistleblowing to help the organisation correct unethical behaviour; perceived ethical orientation to help the organisation prioritise ethics in organisation; two-way communication to facilitate understanding, collaboration, responsiveness in organisation, and reduce suspicion; and improved crisis management to help navigate through the crisis period and achieve success.

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